

Synthesis of Some New Fluorinated Heteroaryl Pyrazolines and Isooxazolines as Potential Biocidal Agents

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Several 1-phenyl-3-(substituted fluorophenyl)-5-heteroaryl- Δ^2 -pyrazolines and 3-(substituted fluorophenyl)-5-heteroaryl- Δ^2 -isooxazolines have been synthesised by condensing fluorinated heteroaryl chalcones with phenyl hydrazine (1) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2), respectively. The title compounds have been screened for their biological activity and the results are discussed.

THE chalcones contain α,β -unsaturated grouping in their molecules and react with phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine affording pyrazolines and isooxazolines, respectively¹⁻⁵. Substituted pyrazolines have been reported as antibacterial⁶⁻¹⁴, antifungal^{6,11-23}, antimicrobial^{24,25}, antiviral²⁶, anti-inflammatory²⁷, diuretic²⁸ and mildewicidal²⁹ agents. It has been found that in pyrazolines the *N*-heterocyclic nucleus incorporated with a carbonyl group show significant biological activity³⁰. Some fluorinated methyliminobenzoxazolines and their derivatives have been patented as plant protecting acaricides, fungicides and insecticides³¹.

In the present work, the preparations of fluorinated heteroaryl pyrazolines and isooxazolines have

been reported. These are derived from previously synthesised fluorinated heteroaryl chalcones³². The general methods adopted by various workers^{1,33-39} for the synthesis of pyrazolines and isooxazolines of potential biological activity involves the reaction between a chalcone and phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride, respectively. The fluorinated heteroaryl chalcones react with phenylhydrazine to yield phenylhydrazones which immediately rearrange to the corresponding isomeric 1-phenyl-3-(substituted fluorophenyl)-5-heteroaryl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline³ (1) in the presence of acetic acid (Scheme A). The isooxazoline (2) derivatives were obtained by treating the pyridine solution of the fluorinated heteroaryl chalcones and aqueous hydroxylamine hydrochloride³ (Scheme B).

where R = α -Furyl, α -thienyl, or α -pyridyl.

R' = 4'-Fluoro, 2'-fluoro-5'-methyl, 4'-fluoro-3'-methyl and 5'-fluoro-2'-hydroxy.

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 1-PHENYL-3-(SUBSTITUTED FLUOROPHENYL)-5-HETEROARYL- Δ^2 -PYRAZOLINES (1)

Compd. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)	
						C	H
1.	Furyl-	4'-Fluoro-	110	82.47	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ON ₂ F	74.45 (74.50)	4.87 (4.90)
2.	Furyl-	4'-Fluoro-3'-methyl-	75	40.62	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ON ₂ F	78.10 (78.12)	5.29 (5.31)
3.	Furyl-	5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxy-	60	50.11	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ F	70.74 (70.80)	4.59 (4.64)
4.	Thienyl-	4'-Fluoro-	95	62.65	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ SN ₂ F	70.78 (70.80)	4.61 (4.64)
5.	Thienyl-	2'-Fluoro-5'-methyl-	90	38.07	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ SN ₂ F	71.33 (71.42)	5.00 (5.06)
6.	Thienyl-	5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxy-	70	49.89	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ OSN ₂ F	67.40 (67.45)	4.39 (4.43)
7.	Furyl-	2'-Fluoro-5'-methyl-	85	35.21	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ON ₂ F	78.10 (78.12)	5.28 (5.31)
8.	Thienyl-	4'-Fluoro-3'-methyl-	65	58.57	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ SN ₂ F	71.40 (71.42)	5.00 (5.06)
9.	Furyl-	2'-Chloro-4'-fluoro-	130	35.31	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ OCIN ₂ F	66.90 (66.96)	4.09 (4.11)
10.	Thienyl-	2'-Chloro-4'-fluoro-	140	34.50	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ SCIN ₂ F	68.90 (69.95)	3.80 (3.92)
11.	Pyridyl-	4'-Fluoro-	85	31.13	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ F	75.00 (75.10)	5.00 (5.04)
12.	Pyridyl-	2'-Fluoro-5'-methyl-	115	36.40	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ F	76.05 (76.10)	5.40 (5.43)

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF DERIVATIVES OF 3-(SUBSTITUTED FLUOROPHENYL)-5-HETEROARYL- Δ^2 -ISOXAZOLINE (2)

Compd. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis% . Found/(Calcd.)	
						C	H
1.	Furyl-	4'-Fluoro-	180	52.36	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ NF	69.30 (69.33)	3.98 (4.00)
2.	Furyl-	4'-Fluoro-3'-methyl-	200	40.81	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ NF	68.50 (68.57)	4.79 (4.81)
3.	Furyl-	5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxy-	210	54.58	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ NF	67.50 (67.53)	4.30 (4.32)
4.	Thienyl-	4'-Fluoro-	140	40.83	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ONSF	63.10 (63.15)	4.00 (4.04)
5.	Thienyl-	2'-Fluoro-5'-methyl-	160	47.12	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ OSNF	64.30 (64.36)	4.58 (4.59)
6.	Thienyl-	5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxy-	190	58.93	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ NSF	59.25 (59.31)	3.75 (3.80)
7.	Pyridyl-	4'-Fluoro-	70	42.63	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₂ F	69.85 (69.41)	4.50 (4.54)
8.	Pyridyl-	2'-Fluoro-5'-methyl-	120	49.42	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ F	70.25 (70.31)	5.75 (5.78)
9.	Pyridyl-	5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxy-	150	47.09	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ F	65.07 (65.11)	4.20 (4.26)

Some of the synthesised compounds have been screened for their antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal activities by standard methods⁴⁰⁻⁴².

Experimental

The purity of the compounds has been checked by tlc. Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The infrared spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 and 177 spectrometers. The physical and analytical data are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

General procedure for synthesis of fluorinated heteroaryl pyrazolines (1): The required amount of

chalcone (4.62 m mol) was added to phenylhydrazine (9.25 m mol) in glacial acetic acid³ (10 ml) and the mixture was refluxed in an oil-bath at 120-130° for 3 h. After cooling, the resultant mass was diluted with water and the solid obtained, was crystallised from ethanol. These derivatives when placed on a filter paper and exposed to bromine vapour, turned green and have been identified as pyrazolines¹. The pyrazolines synthesised are recorded in Table 1.

General procedure for synthesis of fluorinated heteroaryl isoxazolines (2): To a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (17.2 m mol) in water (5 ml) were added, the requisite chalcone (4.62 m mol) and pyridine³ (10 ml). The mixture was refluxed

for 4 h and then acidified with dilute acetic acid and left overnight. The solid, thus obtained was crystallised from benzene after washing with petroleum ether. Synthesised isooxazolines are recorded in Table 2.

Biological screening :

Antiviral activity : The antiviral activity against *Sunnhemp rosette virus* (SRV) of four of the synthesised compounds was evaluated by the method of Verma and Awasthi⁴⁰. The results are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3—ANTIVIRAL ACTIVITY

Sl. no.	Compound	Percentage inhibition of <i>Sunnhemp rosette virus</i> (SRV)	
		<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>
1.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-5-furyl-1-phenyl-Δ ³ -pyrazoline	72.00	43.00
2.	3-(4'-Fluoro-3'-methylphenyl)-5-furyl-1-phenyl-Δ ³ -pyrazoline	80.00	48.00
3.	3-(5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-furyl-Δ ³ -isooxazoline	55.00	49.00
4.	3-(5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-thienyl-Δ ³ -isooxazoline	54.00	-1.00

Antibacterial activity : Ten of the synthesised compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity by disc diffusion method^{41,42}. The bacteria employed for the tests were *Bacillus anthracis*, *Kelebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Corynebacterium pyogenes*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas spp.*, *Escherichie coli* and *Salmonella typhimurim*. The results are recorded in Table 4.

Antifungal activity : The antifungal activity of fifteen synthesised compounds was determined by

adopting the poisoned food technique⁴³ using potato dextrose agar medium. The fungi employed were *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium sativum*. The results are presented in Table 5.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra of pyrazolines 1, 3 and 6 (Table 1) exhibited an intense, sharp bands around 1230, 1150, 1145 cm⁻¹ due to C-N and 1620, 1480, 1650 cm⁻¹ to C=N stretching vibrations. Isooxazolines 1 and 3 (Table 2) showed sharp bands around 825, 870 cm⁻¹ due to N-O and 1660, 1640 cm⁻¹ to C=N stretching vibrations.

The observed values of carbon and hydrogen analysis are in agreement with the calculated values.

In viricidal activity, pyrazolines showed a better activity over isooxazolines (Table 3). The enhancement of this activity in these two series of compounds was observed when a CH₃ group and OH group are in the aromatic ring of pyrazoline and isooxazoline molecules, respectively.

Perusal of Table 4 reveals that most of these compounds were found active against only three bacteria, viz. *B. anthracis*, *C. pyogenes* and *K. pneumoniae*. A good degree of activity was observed only in some of the tested compounds (Table 4; 9, 10) which contain pyridyl nucleus as heteroaryl substituents. Further work is in progress.

In the fungicidal screening most of these compounds possessed fairly good antifungal activity against both the fungi. In general, all the tested compounds were found active against *A. niger*. Pyrozolines again show preponderance over isooxazolines (Table 5). The presence of the following

TABLE 4—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

Sl. no.	Compound	<i>B. ant.</i>	<i>K. pne.</i>	<i>S. Aur.</i>	<i>S. Pyo.</i>	<i>C. Pyo.</i>	<i>P. vul.</i>	<i>P. aer.</i>	<i>E. col.</i>	<i>S. typ.</i>
1.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-5-furyl-1-phenyl-Δ ³ -pyrazoline	++	+	R	R	+	R	R	R	R
2.	3-(4'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-furyl-1-phenyl-Δ ³ -pyrazoline	++	+++	R	R	++	R	R	R	R
3.	3-(4'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-5-thienyl-Δ ³ -pyrazoline	+++	++	R	R	++	R	R	R	R
4.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-5-pyridyl-Δ ³ -pyrazoline	++	+++	R	R	+	R	R	R	R
5.	3-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)-1-phenyl-5-pyridyl-Δ ³ -pyrazoline	+++	++	R	R	++	R	R	R	R
6.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-5-furyl-Δ ³ -isooxazoline	++	++	R	R	++	R	R	R	R
7.	3-(5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-furyl-Δ ³ -isooxazoline	+	+	R	R	+	R	R	R	R
8.	3-(5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-thienyl-Δ ³ -isooxazoline	+++	++	R	R	++	R	R	R	R
9.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-5-pyridyl-Δ ³ -isooxazoline	+++	+++	R	R	+	R	R	R	R
10.	3-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)-5-pyridyl-Δ ³ -isooxazoline	+++	+++	R	R	++	R	R	R	R

+++ = Highly active (90-100%), ++ = moderately active (50-60%), + = less active (30-50%), R = resistant.

TABLE 5—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF FLUORINATED HETEROARYL PYRAZOLINES AND ISOPYRAZOLINES

Sl. no.	Compound	<i>A. niger</i>		<i>Helminthosporium H. sativum</i>	
		1000 ppm	500 ppm	1000 ppm	500 ppm
1.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-5-furyl-1-phenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline	80.20	50.00	54.00	30.00
2.	3-(4'-Fluoro-3'-methylphenyl)-5-furyl-1-phenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline	68.75	49.87	x	x
3.	3-(5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-furyl-1-phenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline	60.00	40.00	38.20	9.80
4.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-5-thienyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline	88.00	38.00	40.00	32.00
5.	3-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)-1-phenyl-5-thienyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline	56.00	19.78	20.00	1.80
6.	3-(5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-5-thienyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline	72.66	20.25	x	x
7.	3-(2'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)-5-furyl-1-phenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline	75.80	39.25	x	x
8.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-5-pyridyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline	84.10	00	x	x
9.	3-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)-1-phenyl-5-pyridyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline	76.28	50.00	x	x
10.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-5-furyl- Δ^2 -isooxazoline	78.19	40.35	70.00	20.00
11.	3-(5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-furyl- Δ^2 -isooxazoline	69.25	50.12	60.37	30.15
12.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-5-thienyl- Δ^2 -isooxazoline	85.12	45.39	30.18	50.07
13.	3-(5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-thienyl- Δ^2 -isooxazoline	76.00	56.00	75.00	38.00
14.	3-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-5-pyridyl- Δ^2 -isooxazoline	80.38	40.29	81.27	34.36
15.	3-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)-5-pyridyl- Δ^2 -isooxazoline	70.12	52.00	74.00	54.48

nucleus in the molecule may be the cause of high activity of such compounds.

Many compounds containing this nucleus have been found to show biological activity^{8,9,12,24,30}.

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